

Polarographic Studies on the Reduction of the Azomethine Bond in Aryl Thiosemicarbazides and the Determination of Hammett Parameters

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The reduction of 4-phenyl substituted thiosemicarbazides gave one, 2-electron transfer, well defined, irreversible, diffusion controlled reduction waves. The studies were made in Britton-Robinson buffer (pH range 2.0-11.0). The reduction in these compounds takes place at azomethine bond, formed due to a change in structure in alkaline medium. The effect of substituents on the reduction site and its correlation with Hammett substituent constants (σ_x) have been studied. A possible mechanism for their reduction at DME has been proposed.

THE polarographic behaviour of sulphhydryl compounds at the dropping mercury electrode has been studied^{1,2} intensively during the past few years. Since this class is one of the most important among biologically important compounds, its oxidation reduction potential is of much importance. Thiosemicarbazides, well known precursors of antituberculous³, antifertility⁴ and antineoplastic agents, have not been studied polarographically so far.

The present communication deals with the polarographic reduction of these compounds and the effect of various substituents on its half-wave potential and its correlation with the Hammett substituent constant (σ_x).

Experimental

Preparation of thiosemicarbazides: The 4-phenyl substituted thiosemicarbazides, having substituents hydrogen, 2-methyl, 3-methyl, 4-methyl, 2-methoxy, 3-methoxy, 4-methoxy, 2-chloro, 3-chloro, 4-chloro, 2-ethoxy and 2, 5-dimethyl, were prepared according to the method given in literature⁵.

Solutions: 0.01 M stock solutions of 4-phenyl substituted thiosemicarbazides were freshly prepared in dimethylformamide. Britton-Robinson buffers⁶ and 1 M KCl solution were prepared in double distilled water from AnalaR grade chemicals.

Apparatus: Polarographic curves were recorded using a Cambridge pen recording polarograph. The capillary used possessed the characteristics 3.75 mg^{2/3} S^{-1/3} at a zero applied voltage. For the determination of the pH value of the solutions ELICO pH meter model LI-10, fitted with a glass-electrode was used. The number of electrons consumed in the electrode process was determined by the millicoulometry method of DeVries and Kroon⁷

in a small volume (0.3 ml) using a mercury pool as cathode.

Results and Discussion

The polarographic behaviour of all these 4-phenyl substituted thiosemicarbazides was studied in the pH range 2.0-11.0. One well developed reduction wave was observed for all these compounds at pH above 7.0. The slope of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plots for all these thiosemicarbazides lie in the range 0.060-0.067 V/pH, which indicates that all substituted thiosemicarbazides reduce by similar mechanism. However, no wave was obtained below pH ~7.0. This can be accounted for on the basis of change in structure in alkaline medium. Thio form of thiosemicarbazides (Ia) changes into thiol form (Ib or Ic). Such changes of thio form to

thiol form in alkaline medium have also been reported by other workers⁸. Since the change in structure produce $-C=N-$ as a site for facile reduction, the polarographic wave is obtained only in alkaline medium.

All these thiosemicarbazides reduce in a one, 2-electron transfer, diffusion controlled reduction waves. A few typical polarograms have been depicted in Fig. 1. The change in $E_{1/2}$ with increasing concentrations of depolarizer suggests the irreversible nature of the waves (Table 1). The diffusion character of the limiting current has been proved by the linear dependence of the wave height on the concentration of thiosemicarbazides and by the proportionality of the wave height to the square root of the mercury column.

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Fig. 1. Polarograms of o-tolylthiosemicarbazide at various concentrations.

TABLE 1—HALF-WAVE POTENTIALS OF 4-PHENYLTHIOSEMICARBAZIDES AT VARIOUS CONCENTRATIONS

No.	R	Concentrations			
		0.416 × 10 ⁻³ M	0.832 × 10 ⁻³ M	0.125 × 10 ⁻³ M	0.166 × 10 ⁻³ M
		E _{1/2} (V)	E _{1/2} (V)	E _{1/2} (V)	E _{1/2} (V)
I	H	-1.20	-1.20	-1.26	-1.28
II	2-CH ₃	-1.20	-1.20	-1.27	-1.30
III	3-CH ₃	-1.22	-1.26	-1.30	-1.31
IV	4-CH ₃	-1.20	-1.26	-1.30	-1.34
V	2-OCH ₃	-1.20	-1.28	-1.30	-1.32
VI	3-OCH ₃	-1.20	-1.21	-1.28	-1.30
VII	4-OCH ₃	-1.22	-1.22	-1.28	-1.30
VIII	2-Cl	-1.26	-1.28	-1.32	-1.34
IX	3-Cl	-1.26	-1.30	-1.38	-1.40
X	4-Cl	-1.26	-1.33	-1.35	-1.37
XI	2-OC ₂ H ₅	-1.34	-1.36	-1.38	-1.39
XII	4-OC ₂ H ₅	-1.22	-1.26	-1.29	-1.32
XIII	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	-1.23	-1.26	-1.30	-1.32

The following mechanism based on two electron transfer can be proposed for the reduction of azomethine bond in these thiosemicarbazides. Similar reduction steps of the reduction of semicarbazones have also been proposed by Zuman⁹.

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF SOME 4-PHENYLTHIOSEMICARBAZIDES AT pH 10.0 IN 1.0 M KCl, Conc. = 0.832 × 10⁻³ M

No.	R	-E _{1/2} , V	i _d , µA	D ₀ ^{1/2} × 10 ⁻⁵	αn	k ₀ ^{1/2} × 10 ⁻¹⁰ cm ⁻¹	σx
I	H	1.32	1.75	0.32	0.54	1.90	0.00
II	2-CH ₃	1.31	1.70	0.30	0.56	1.60	-0.17
III	3-CH ₃	1.33	1.70	0.30	0.54	1.70	-0.17
IV	4-CH ₃	1.34	1.80	0.38	0.54	1.77	-0.39
V	2-OCH ₃	1.32	1.70	0.30	0.57	1.75	-0.11
VI	3-OCH ₃	1.33	1.75	0.32	0.54	1.67	-0.27
VII	4-OCH ₃	1.35	1.75	0.32	0.56	1.65	+0.20
VIII	2-Cl	1.28	1.80	0.38	0.56	1.65	+0.37
IX	3-Cl	1.29	1.70	0.30	0.57	1.67	+0.23
X	4-Cl	1.30	1.70	0.30	0.54	1.89	-0.35
XI	2-OC ₂ H ₅	1.32	1.80	0.38	0.54	1.86	-0.23
XII	4-OC ₂ H ₅	1.34	1.75	0.32	0.57	1.70	-0.24
XIII	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	1.30	1.70	0.30	0.59	1.70	

Controlled potential electrolysis further suggests 2 electron reduction mechanism for phenylthiosemicarbazide. Four electron reduction mechanism would have resulted in the production of aniline

(-N=C-4H⁺, 4e⁻ → -NH₂ + -CH₃). Products were isolated after electrolysis for about 12 hr at 1.6 V in a H shaped cell and did not give any dye test for aromatic amine. Moreover, on analysing the products by tlc and taking aniline as reference, there was no indication of the presence of aniline. This clearly support 2 electron mechanism for the reduction of phenylthiosemicarbazides.

The E_{1/2} was found to shift towards more negative potential with increase in concentration of the depolarizer (Table 1). Such type of change in E_{1/2} values suggests the irreversible nature of the waves. The plots of E_{d.e.} vs [log $\frac{i}{i_d - i}$ - 0.546 log t] were

found linear. The values of αn and K₀^{1/2} calculated from the slope and intercept, further suggests the irreversible nature of the waves.

It is observed from Table 2 that the half-wave potentials are shifted towards more negative potential for compounds with substituents having electron donating nature, viz., 2-CH₃, 3-CH₃, 4-CH₃, 2-OCH₃, 3-OCH₃, 4-OCH₃, 2-Cl, 3-Cl, 4-Cl, 2-OC₂H₅, 4-OC₂H₅ and 2,5-(CH₃)₂. This behaviour can be accounted for by considering the effect of the substituents. An electron donating group on the benzene ring would increase electron density on carbon attached to the hetero atom, viz., nitrogen due to which the reduction would become less facile and the E_{1/2} would shift to more negative potentials.

Correlation of half-wave potential with Hammett constants: The correlation between the structure of compounds and their chemical reactivity is a fundamental problem in organic chemistry. One of the most important and versatile of these correlations is the Hammett equation¹⁰ which relates the effect of structure on the reactivity of the molecule.

For application in polarography, Hammett equation is transformed to the form¹¹

$$\Delta E_{1/2} = P + M + S,$$

where P, M and S represent the shift in the half-wave potential due to the change in activation energy by polar, mesomeric and steric effects. In *m*- or *p*-substituted thiosemicarbazides the substituents are rigid and lie much away from the reaction centre with the result that generally the steric interaction between the substituent and reaction centre is almost negligible. The change in $E_{1/2}$ of parent thiosemicarbazide can, therefore, be attributed to the electron repelling nature of the substituent. Thus, when steric effects are not taken into account, the modified Hammett equation,

$$\Delta E_{1/2} \cong \rho_{\pi, R} \sigma X,$$

represents the polar effect of the substituents. Considering the relationship for the substituent effect¹²

$$\sigma X \cong \log k_1 - \log k_1^0$$

where k_1^0 and k_1 represent the ionisation constants for the unsubstituted and substituted molecules, respectively and σX is the substituent constant. The corresponding relationship for the irreversible wave may be written as

$$\sigma X \cong \log k_{f,h(\text{sub})}^0 - \log k_{f,h(\text{unsub})}^0$$

The value of σX at pH 10.0 thus determined are given in Table 2.

Fig. 2 exhibits the relation between $E_{1/2}$ of substituted thiosemicarbazides and the Hammett sub-

Fig. 2. Plot of $-E_{1/2}$ vs σ for some 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide in B. R. buffer at pH=10.0.

stituent constant σX , which include both polar induction and polar configuration effect. It is of interest to note that substituents like 3-Cl, 4-Cl, 3-CH₃, 4-CH₃, 4-OCH₃ and 4-OC₂H₅ fit in the straight line, whereas 2-Cl, 2-CH₃, 2-OCH₃, 2-OC₂H₅ and 2,5-(CH₃)₂ show deviation. This deviation may be accounted for on the basis of slight steric hindrance to coplanarity. The value of specific rate constant (ρ) was found to be 0.12 V.

It is observed in the above reaction series that methyl, chloro, methoxy and ethoxy substituents show positive polarographic *ortho* shift which indicates that *ortho* derivative is easily reducible in comparison to its *p*-analogue.

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC *ortho* SHIFTS (Δ_0) FOR SOME 4-PHENYLTHIOSEMICARBAZIDES AT pH 10.0.

R	Δ_0 , V
Methyl	+0.03
Chloro	+0.02
Methoxy	+0.03
Ethoxy	+0.02

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